

26.5% tillers were damaged — much more than in the previous 2 years. But a shortage of rain in that area in October greatly reduced the overwintering gall midge population.

In Trad province, eastern Thailand, the population increased, especially on rice variety RD1. Although the percentage of galls on RD1 was relatively low, the plants were heavily stunted and yields were greatly reduced. Gall midge survival in the area was probably high because of low parasitization by *Platygaster* spp. (Table 2). For the first

Table 2. Survival of the rice gall midge at various locations in Thailand, 1979 wet season.

Location	Galls observed (no.)	Survival (%)	Mortality (%) caused by			
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>P. folsteri</i>	<i>N. gracillius</i>	Unknown
Lam-Ngob, Trad	103	80.6	0	0	18.4	1.0
Ban Ta Kak, Trad	117	70.9	0	0	24.8	4.3
Bau, Chantaburi	123	48.0	17.1	0.8	30.0	4.1
Ban Don Chik, Ubonratchatani	126	22.2	3.2	0	68.3	6.3
Ban Pa Rauk, Chiengrai	137	46.8	36.5	10.2	2.9	3.6

time, a gall midge outbreak was reported in Chantaburi. About 175 ha of local rice varieties in Bau district were heavily infested.

The abundance of wild host plants favors the survival of overwintering populations in the northern and eastern areas. ■

Gall midge occurrence in Uttar Pradesh, India

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Gall midge in serious proportions was observed in more than 2,000 ha in Faizabad district of U.P. in kharif 1978. The pest was observed only once earlier — in kharif 1971 — in the state. Most of the area infested in 1978 was contiguous; in some pockets the incidence was as high as 65%. The late-planted crop of Saket 4, Jaya, and IR8 were affected most. At the Masodha Rice Research Station, IET2232, IR24, Reshmi, NP5136, FHI, FH109, Satna, Belar, Ranga, FRG2, and FRG19 were also found severely affected by the pest. The incidence was observed from late August to mid-October. ■

Parasitization of BPH eggs in rice treated with foliar insecticide

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Sprays of the insecticides decamethrin, methyl parathion, and diazinon have caused resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) in IRRI fields; Perthane spray has not. Laboratory studies indicated that those insecticides stimulate BPH

BPH egg parasitization (%)

Percentage of parasitization of brown planthopper (BPH) eggs on rice sprayed with foliar insecticides. Arrows indicate days after transplanting (18, 39, 61 DT) when the insecticides were sprayed. IRRI, 1979 dry season.

reproduction, but their role in causing field resurgence by suppressing natural enemies has not been determined. Thus, a study was conducted to determine the effect of the insecticides on BPH egg parasitization, using the technique of Otake.

Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings were planted in clay pots (15 cm diam) at the rate of 4 seedlings/pot. When the plants were 30 to 40 days old, 20 gravid BPH were released into cylindrical mylar film cages covering each pot. Twenty-four hours later, the hoppers